

A Chatbot Assistant for Optimizing the Fault Detection and Diagnostics of Industry 4.0 Equipment in the 6G era

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Abstract—This paper focuses on optimizing the fault detection and diagnostics of equipment maintenance of the Factory of the Future (FoF) in the 6G era. To take advantage of the novel features that the future mobile communication networks are offering this paper proposes the use of a Chatbot assistant that is powered with context awareness of the factory machinery and indoor locations by interfacing with the 3GPP APIs of the core network for realizing a Human-Robot cooperation in the manufacturing environment. The benefits of the proposed chatbot-assisted approach are evaluated in a quantitative way by introducing four KPIs related to the phases of the fault detection and diagnostics process and assessing them by the number of actions required for the completion of each one of them. Our assessment shows that the proposed approach leads to a significant reduction of the required complexity compared to the traditional manual process.

Keywords—6G; 5G; FoF; Industry 4.0; Chatbot; NEF; 3GPP

I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of the Factory of the Future (FoF) entails a manufacturing vision in which assembly lines are totally automated and highly configurable. This is achieved through the use of cutting-edge Information and Communications Technologies (ICT) and by leveraging advancements in the interaction between human workers and machines, through Augmented Reality (AR) and remote-control capabilities. More specifically, in the concept of Industry 4.0 [1] human centered automation is one of the milestones that is envisioned in order to achieve this objective, where modules will no longer be linked by wires and will instead be connected to each other via ultra-high-performance radio links. This permits them to freely roam around the assembly line, allowing for the quick formation of custom assembly lines [2]. Artificial Intelligence (AI) and digital twin technologies will allow us to collect manufacturing knowledge and experience and then share it with machines and robots to improve manufacturing.

Towards this, the FoF strives for full automation and flexibility in order to fulfill the demands of mass customization. The 6G network will be critical in enabling this transition. The utilization of ultra-high performance radio links,

which untether machines from connecting cables, is required for modules to freely move about in order to rapidly construct a customized assembly line [3].

Furthermore, with AI and digital twins, machines and robots will be able to acquire and exchange manufacturing experience and knowledge, assisting in the optimization of the expanding manufacturing process. 6G could potentially provide numerous advantages to the FoF, such as an effective interface between physical and cyber world, playing in real time the connector role between human, sensors, robots, and big data towards the 6G-envisioned cyber-physical continuum, where the network platform should not only connect humans and machines but will be able to fully merge realities, allowing seamless interaction and immersive experiences.

Among the various AI-enabled technologies, Chatbots [4] are the best candidate for realizing the first step of Human-Robot cooperation in a manufacturing environment, since they can act as assistants of engineers in the factory, using the data gained from sensors to guide the engineers and technicians during daily workflows, as well as predicting and warning the respective engineers for dangerous conditions.

A first milestone towards converging the physical world of the factory employees with the cyber world of the factory machinery is to provide to the Chatbot app a context awareness by integrating it, as vertical application enabler, to the 3GPP-compliant network infrastructure of the factory. One of the main advantages that Chatbot offers is the 24/7 availability. Furthermore, the AI-powered conversational intelligence gives the Chatbot the capability of humanlike interactions. Also, AI-powered Chatbots can undertake numerous queries simultaneously at any given moment. Hence, the presence of a Chatbot directly impacts the scale at which the factory can operate.

With the previous assertions in mind, the rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the tools used for the Chatbot development. In Section III a detailed description of the use case scenario is presented. Section IV compares the efficiency of our proposed solution against the traditional one. Finally, a discussion and ideas for future work are presented in Section V.

II. BACKGROUND

A. NEF APIs

The exposure of network capabilities, within the framework of 3GPP, was introduced in Rel. 13 of the specifications as Service Capabilities Exposure Function (SCEF). The design of SCEF allows for a secure expose of the services provided by the 3GPP standardized network interfaces.

The Network Exposure Function (NEF) has an equivalent role as the SCEF in Evolved Packet System (EPS). It makes use of several of the exposure capabilities defined in SCEF and adapts them in order to be compliant with the new Service Based Architecture (SBA). While 4G mainly provides throughput-based services, 5G is focusing more on the vertical industries and 6G envisions a more user-centric network [5].

The NEF consists of many services that can be described as Monitoring services, Application Provisioning services, Policy and Charging services, Industry 4.0 / Internet of Things (IoT) specific services, Analytics services, and Security services [5].

Within the mobile network coverage, a User Equipment (UE) goes through different stages in terms of availability, connectivity, and location awareness. There are scenarios that this knowledge is proving to be valuable for an external 6G/5G-enabled application. One example is when an application needs to have information about the indoor location of its users, e.g., within an industrial zone, in order to reach to authorization decisions for the personnel. Thus, the monitoring of UE's status by an external application, e.g., a mobile app within a 5G System (5GS) and/or a 6G system (6GS) can be accomplished through the MonitoringEvent API of 3GPP NEF, which supports location reporting and connectivity events. For the needs of this paper, this API was also utilised for Chatbot assistant for optimizing the fault detection and diagnostics of Industry 4.0 Equipment.

This ability to pinpoint exact locations is a crucial feature of the Chatbot assistant, since it can create context awareness to the user based on the information that the network provides to the application. 6G/5G networks divide the location services into three categories based on which component is responsible for the initiation of the location reporting. The first category includes the Network Induced Location Requests (NI-LR) which are initiated by an Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF) to determine a UE's location on behalf of a regulatory agency (e.g., to determine location during an IP Multimedia Subsystem (IMS) emergency call). The second category contains the Mobile Terminated Location Requests (MT-LR), These requests are initiated by internal or external Location Service (LCS) client which can be a third-party application accessed by the UE, regulatory agencies, or mobile network operators. The third category includes the Mobile Originated Location Requests (MO-LR) which are initiated by the UE to determine its own location or to provide its location to an external client. This last category (MO-LR) is the method that was selected for advancing the capabilities of the chatbot assistant in order to improve the maintenance process in a FoF ecosystem.

B. Tools for the Main Chatbot App

Chatbots are stateless online applications that usually utilize AI-mechanisms to take decisions and are categorized to three main classes: The menu-driven chatbots, the NLP-driven chatbots and the hybrid ones.

The menu-driven chatbots are based on a simplified user interface with a tree-based menu, which can be either pre-defined based on specific rules or dynamically defined based on dynamic AI-decisions. The menu-driven chatbots simplify the interaction of the user with the bot by minimizing the required complexity to respond to a specific question, since the user feeds the chatbot with data easily by selecting the appropriate button from a prompt menu, but on the other hand optimizes a specific process by limiting the required time and effort needed to complete a specific task.

The NLP-driven chatbots offer a more advanced conversational interface, which provides more sophisticated and advanced replies to the user, utilizing generative AI techniques. These chatbots require the tighter engagement of the user by typing questions and/or elaborating more on the provided answers, making the interaction between the user and the chatbot app more time-consuming and complicated. This type of chatbots is usually selected for assisting a user to a specific analytic task, rather than for optimizing the required time and minimizing the effort needed of completing a specific task.

Finally, hybrid chatbots that combine both menu-based and NLP-based reactions are also available, usually serving multiple scopes and objectives.

Chatbots are often created using Javascript using a framework like Node.js and a well-known messaging service's API. The functioning of Chatbots is built on event emitters. In the case of the BotMan framework that was used for the needs of the hybrid type Chatbot that is introduced in this paper, the following message types are supported: Text Message, URL Message, Contact Message, Picture Message, Video Message, Location Message, Sticker Message, File Message, and Rich Media Message.

The Chatbot app in order to communicate with the messaging platform, it is necessary to use a server that will receive, process and send back messages. The server will make use of the BotMan API since this is the primary way to get data in and out of the Chatbot platform. The server must have an endpoint URL (Webhook) that is accessible from BotMan's server and all new subscriptions to the service must use a secure HTTPS callback URL. Currently, there are many cloud-based services that are suitable for the development of the Chatbot sector. Among the various alternatives, for the

Fig. 1. Chatbot deployment.

deployment needs of the Chatbot app of this paper, as shown in Fig. 1, Heroku hosting service for managing stateless Node.js web application was selected, which has many similarities to serverless environments.

III. THE FAULT DETECTION AND DIAGNOSTICS PROCESS

Early equipment maintenance was limited to simple regular maintenance based on predetermined time intervals and fixing broken assets. Even if they wanted to, maintenance specialists couldn't have been more proactive. They simply lacked the capacity to gather, store, and evaluate data on the performance and health of the equipment. Today, the way in which equipment maintenance is executed has undergone a substantial transformation as a result of ongoing developments in microprocessor-based controls, automation, real-time data collecting, and systems like Fault Detection and Diagnostics (FDD). The advances in 6G and 5G systems private networks, as well as in Industry 5.0/4.0 automations can further transform and automate the FDD process, offering novel ways of interaction between the employees and the machines. Private 6G/5G cellular networks are mainly used to link devices belonging to a private FoF environment. They provide several advantages over typical wireless networks, such as higher data throughput, reduced latency, and the ability to connect to more devices. This means for manufacturers:

- The capacity to acquire and process data more rapidly, leading to better decision-making and productivity.
- Response times that are faster for applications requiring real-time communication, such as robots and autonomous cars
- The capability of interconnecting a large number of equipment and sensors

Furthermore, private 6G/5G cellular networks are more secure than private Wi-Fi networks because they employ specific radio frequencies, end-to-end encryption, and are readily incorporated into existing security systems. Moreover, a 6G/5G private network realizes 3GPP NEF APIs that offer a programmable environment, which offers network capabilities exposure of the 5G Core toward external applications integrated with the 3GPP network and allows to developers to design new service logic.

A. New FDD process by NEF-enabled Chatbot Assistants

Chatbots are considered the most promising automated assistants among the other alternatives, since they offer a

simple but still efficient way to interact with the user and automate a specific process. In the case of FDD and Industry 5.0/4.0, chatbot assistants are expected to create pipelines of actions that will occur in a factory environment to optimize and quicken the management of maintenance phases. By adding capabilities offered by 3GPP NEF APIs, chatbots can transform how FDD and maintenance scenarios are occurring in a factory. By exploiting 3GPP NEF APIs, a Chatbot assistant can be introduced as a new mechanism of reporting malfunctions and facilitating the planning of the required actions in order to address and fix the reported issues more efficiently in terms of time, cost and performance.

The Chatbot inclusion in the FDD process will assist in automating the steps currently needed for the identification and the solution of possible malfunctions in a shorter time frame using a user-friendly interface. By exploiting the capability of the mobile network to provide an Identification ID for each connected worker inside the factory and his/her relative indoor location, the chatbot assistant can provide the necessary match making process between the detected fault and the appropriate authorized technician. The chatbot assisted FDD process that will be followed in a FoF environment is listed below:

1) Automated Worker Status Authorization

Initially, the Chatbot obtains the worker's indoor location, for example the worker is in Area A. After checking whether the determined area is safe, and hence the evacuation procedure is not initiated, next the access status of the worker in Area A is checked. In the case in which the person does not have clearance to perform any actions in the designated area, he/she is prompted to leave and a worker with the appropriate clearance is notified.

2) Automated Reporting process

If the worker is cleared the predefined reporting procedure is initiated. The worker interacts with the Chatbot and follows the indications that appear on the Chatbot interface to report the problem in a proper way.

3) Automated listing of the Service Manuals based on 3GPP NEF APIs

5G openness provides the location information of the cell that a UE is connected, which can be used directly by the service in order to gain location awareness of the workers. Indeed, a locally installed 5G network has the potential to offer such indoor localization information of each connected UE based on the APIs provided by NEF and more specifically by

Fig. 2. Depiction of the use case. The closest worker to the faulty machinery does not have clearance to perform any actions to the designated area and thus the Chatbot notifies the next closest worker with the appropriate clearance.

Fig. 3. Interaction between Chatbot and MonitoringEvent API.

the MonitoringEvent API and the location reporting event and the aspects that it provides. In this sense, the factory will be mapped into cells according to the coverage of the installed 5G small cell antennas. The respective database will indicate the machines that fall under each of the factory areas providing the functionality of a specific machines' list.

Thus, after the reporting procedure has been completed, the worker is presented with the option to make a request for the machine's manuals in order to fix the damaged machinery. Instead of manually inserting a unique machine identifier, the procedure is automated by the NEF-enabled chatbot, which narrows the list of the available machines down to the ones near the authorized maintenance worker based on the worker location as it is reported by the Mobile Core Network and specifically the 3GPP NEF APIs. With that approach, the workers can easily search for the machine that they are interested in, fetch on their mobile device all the related and useful documentation, and finally perform any necessary action, only with the support of the Chatbot device.

Finally, even in the occasion that the problem is not resolved at that time, an issue which will include a documentation report on the fault, will remain active. A depiction of the chatbot automations in FDD is presented in Fig. 2.

B. NEF Interaction Description

3GPP has introduced the concept of Vertical Application Enablers (VAEs) in Rel. 16 [8] enabling the efficient use and deployment of vertical apps over 3GPP systems. The main focus of VAEs is to provide key capabilities, such as message distribution, service continuity, application resource management, dynamic group management and vertical application server APIs utilizing the 5G system. Thus, the concept of VAE is deemed important in order to fully exploit the capabilities that the exposure of NEF provides.

Moreover, 3GPP adopts the client-server model implied by the REpresentational State Transfer (REST) paradigm. The main difference is that the client and server are named as service consumers and service producers, respectively and that the asynchronous calls are supported as well. With the asynchronous sequence the service consumers can be notified any time an event occurs.

In the light of the above premise, the interaction of the Chatbot with the MonitoringEvent API provided by NEF is illustrated in Fig. 3 and is composed into three main steps. The

first step describes the successful subscription of the VAE to the NEF and the interaction where the latter sends a call back notification to the former asynchronously. Moreover, in order to support the asynchronous notification, the VAE implements its own RESTful API for the call back notification, which corresponds to the second step of the process. The VAE, based on the user ID, will request from the API to retrieve the location info of the user. It then correlates the UE-location provided by the API to specific areas of the factory. The VAE has been properly configured in order to be aware of the factory areas and be able to map the retrieved 5G UE location to each of them. Finally, the notification is received by Chatbot, including the requested data.

IV. ASSESSMENT OF NEF-ENABLED CHATBOT IN FDD PROCESS

Different forms of maintenance have varied levels of danger, upfront expenditures, and manpower needs. Instead of implementing a single kind of maintenance strategy throughout your facility, you may assign various assets to distinct maintenance plans. For example, predictive analytics are often required for industrial equipment maintenance, whereas property maintenance is more reactive.

Due to this diversity, the use of a chatbot assistant can significantly minimize the complexity and the cost of the various maintenance types, since it automates various processes that are needed, which are time-consuming and involve various actors and employees in their execution.

Among the various types of maintenance, such as preventive, predictive, reactive, corrective, and usage-based, the performance validation of the chatbot use in the maintenance procedure is performed on a corrective maintenance type.

To assess the effectiveness of a chatbot assistant in the FDD process, the 6G Network app and the Chatbot Virtual Assistant were deployed in the 5G/6G experimentation platform that is available in Athens [9]. For the quantified assessment and the validation of the proposed solution, we introduce four KPIs that represent the main phases that are followed in a FDD process. These four KPIs are the following ones:

- **KPI#1:** Fault Detection and authorized technician notification
- **KPI#2:** Fault isolation and fault identification
- **KPI#3:** Fault evaluation and repair
- **KPI#4:** Repair validation and completion

The assessment of each KPI is performed in a quantitative way by counting the number of steps needed to complete the specific FDD phase that represents this KPI.

Therefore, according to Table I, 10 steps should be followed today in order to complete today a corrective maintenance FDD task without the use of a chatbot assistant.

TABLE I. KPIS ASSESSMENT FOR COMPLETING A CORRECTIVE MAINTENANCE FDD TASK WITHOUT A CHABOT ASSISTANT

KPI	KPI Value	Steps needed to complete a corrective maintenance FDD task
Fault Detection and authorized technician notification	2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The closest, in proximity, technician is examining the potential failure. 2. Then an authorised/specialised technician is asked to go onsite to confirm the machine failure.
Fault isolation and fault identification	4	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. A failure report must be completed prior to carrying out corrective maintenance tasks in order for the production process to be suspended. 4. The authorised/specialised technician requests the service manual for the specific equipment in order to follow the necessary steps to repair the failure. 5. Based on the provided documentation, the technicians identify in which part of the entire system the fault has happened. 6. The authorised/specialised technician then uses safety management software to reduce safety risks and hazards in workplaces.
Fault evaluation and repair	2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. The authorised/specialised technician then uses inspection software to conduct assessments as needed. 8. Then the authorised/specialised technician repairs or replaces the faulty part or item in the equipment.
Repair validation and completion	2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 9. Then the authorised/specialised technician validates the performance before returning the system to service. 10. Finally, the authorised/specialised technician fills in a repair report in order to request the re-initiation of the production process.

TABLE II. KPIS ASSESSMENT FOR COMPLETING A CORRECTIVE MAINTENANCE FDD TASK WITH A CHABOT ASSISTANT

KPI	KPI Value	Steps needed to complete a corrective maintenance FDD task
Fault Detection and authorized technician notification	1	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The failure is automatically identified by the sensors that are deployed across the production line and the Chatbot notifies directly an authorised/specialised technician to go onsite to confirm the machine failure.
Fault isolation and fault identification	2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. The failure report is completed digitally via the Chatbot app and the production process is suspended automatically, while using the context-aware Chatbot menu, the authorised/specialised technician downloads the service manual for the specific equipment. 3. Based on the provided documentation, the technician identifies in which part of the entire system the fault has happened and the Chatbot guides the technician step-by-step in order to reduce safety risks and hazards in workplaces
Fault evaluation and repair	1	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. The authorised/specialised technician then uses the Chatbot app in order to conduct assessments as needed, using the data that the Chatbot receives via the core network and the sensors of the industry. If the assessment is failing, then the authorised/specialised technician repairs or replaces the faulty part or item in the equipment.
Repair validation and completion	2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Then the authorised/specialised technician validates the performance before returning the system to service. 6. Finally, the authorised/specialised technician fills in a repair report in order to request the re-initiation of the production process.

With the introduction of the Chatbot as a virtual assistant and the context awareness that the Chatbot gains by its integration with the NEF APIs of the cellular communication system's core network, a significant reduction of the steps needed in order to streamline the necessary repair process is achieved as Table II presents.

More specifically it is observed that the steps required for the achievement of each KPI of the FDD phases are significantly reduced by 50%, apart from the last KPI that refers to the Repair validation and completion, which is not affected by the use of the chatbot. This is a significant improvement in the performance and efficiency of the FDD process since on the one hand the time required is reduced and on the other hand the accuracy and the efficiency of the executed tasks is improved.

This enhancement is a representative example on how 6G network can provide user and human-centric services by fusing information that is available by the core network and the physical world. The Internet of Everything (IoE), a fully integrated, internet-based system facilitating communication between users, devices, and the environment, is anticipated to be introduced by 6G and this Proof of Concept (PoC) implementation of such as use-case proves that this fusion impacts positively the performance of the fused use-case and service.

Fig. 4. Comparison of KPIs in FDD with and without the use of chatbot

In order to better understand and visualize the performance enhancements that the use of a NEF-enabled chatbot assistant

introduces to the FDD process, Fig. 4 represents a spider diagram of the KPIs of Table I and Table II.

According to the assessed KPIs and Fig.4, it is evident that the use of the NEF-enabled Chatbot introduces a significant optimization in the FDD process by improving all the four KPIs and minimizing the steps required in order to complete the activity. More specifically the automation and the context awareness between the physical and the cyber world that the NEF-enabled chatbot introduces, manages to achieve a performance improvement in corrective maintenance by 40% in the number of the steps required to complete the action.

V. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

Repair and maintenance are a crucial part of every industrial enterprise due to the connection with the performance and the productivity of the entire business. The benefits introduced to the FoF through the use of a Chatbot assistant, as far as the corrective maintenance process is concerned, are displayed in this paper. Nonetheless, as previously stated, the Chatbot app constitutes the first milestone to the human-machine interaction that is taking place in the concept of Industry 4.0.

The next step is the use of Extended Reality (XR) cloud services and holographic display which are expected to become one of the main human-centric applications in 6G, which are realizing in the physical world the virtual character of a chatbot app. The introduction of XR can lead to an interactive environment where the technicians would be able to see the real object augmented with digital elements, what tools they need to complete the task, and even receive instructions on how to proceed. The machine's specs, details, and history could be represented visually in the form of XR tags, leading to a better understanding of the situation and higher probability to solve the problem.

In the context of industrial repair and maintenance applications, XR provides the benefits presented below:

- Fewer human errors since technicians can learn new skills and build new knowledge by collaborating with an expert in real-time or by following carefully designed interactive procedures.
- Safety hazards are being reduced by allowing employees to have access to safety information and procedures which are related to individual pieces of machinery.
- Faster diagnostics and repairs due to the ability of XR technology to provide a digital overlay of the relevant repair instructions on the actual problem.

Although 5G has been designed with high reliability and low latency, some cases introduce extremely high requirements that exceed 5G's capabilities. 6G will enable these use cases through technologies that support ultra-high reliability, extreme low latency, and deterministic communication capability.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The Fault Detection and Diagnostics process is essential for the successful realization of the Industry 4.0 vision. With the

evolution of the factory machinery to more autonomous systems, the complexity of the FDD steps has significantly increased. 6G networks are expected to play a significant role in simplifying the required steps and minimizing the complexity that is currently required in order to complete efficiently the FDD process. By exploiting the vision that 6G provides a user- and human-centric network, which expands the context awareness of the user from the physical world to the virtual/digital world, this paper has provided a PoC implementation of a 6G network app that uses a chatbot assistant to enhance the performance of the FDD process in Industry 4.0 environments. The performance evaluation of the proposed implementation shows that the new merged reality of the digital and physical world can improve the efficiency of the FDD process by 50%.

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